

A Study on Neo Banking Trends in India

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Abstract

The Banking industry is facing so many challenges today. Many banks in the public sector are in trouble with the increase in Non Performing Assets. Neo Banks is the type of banks which provide digital services. Some banks have started their own neo banking operations. Many start-ups have collaborated to a banking licensee to launch digital start-ups. The neo bank market is growing at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 50.6% during the period 2017-2020. So, this study aims to have an understanding of the new trend in the banking industry- Neo Banks.

Keywords: Neo Banks, Fin Tech enterprises, banking.

Introduction

Neo bank is a type of direct bank that is 100% digital and reaches customers on mobile applications and personal computer platforms only. They are Fin-Tech enterprises which provide banking services in collaboration with an existing bank. They do not have a banking license. They are also known as challenger banks.

According to a survey conducted by Tech Foliance (a business intelligence service provider), there are about 50 Fin-Tech organizations all over the world.

Atom Bank (Britain), Buddy bank(Italy), Civilized Bank (Britain), Go Bank (USA), Loot bank(USA), We bank (China), N26 (Europe) Yono by SBI (India), Open (India) are major neo banks operating in the world.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the concept of Neo Banking
- To understand the new trends in neo banking in India.

History of Indian Banking Sector

The banking system has drastically changed, leaving no trace of the old ways. Fourteen major commercial banks accounting for 70 percent of the resources of the banking system had been nationalized in 1969. In the second phase, six banks were nationalized. Today 91 commercial banks with 141756 branches are functioning in India.

The nationalization brought tremendous changes in the banking industry of India. The loans and advances which are available only for the socially forwarded people had become available for lower sections, including rural areas. Pradhan Mantri Jandhan Yojana is the World's largest financial inclusion program; where 36.06 crore new accounts were opened (28.65 in the public sector and 1.25 in the private sector). Many banks in the public sector are in trouble with the increase in Non Performing Assets. Small banks are merging with big ones. All the subsidiary banks of State Bank of India and Mahila Bank were amalgamated with State Bank of India. The new industrial policy of 1991 has increased competition in the banking industry. Public sector banks are facing high competition with private sector new generation banks. Government is taking measures to reduce participation in public sector banks. Government participation in State Bank of India is only 57.88% now.

Neo Banking

As per Global Fin-Tech Report, 28% of the traditional banking transactions are now carrying through Fin-Tech companies. The term Neo Bank first became prominent in 2017 to describe Fin-Tech based financial service providers that were challenging the traditional banking system. There were two main types of neo banking companies, that provide the services digitally and applied for their banking license; and companies that have a partnership with a traditional bank to provide those types of financial services.

Today, major global banks have been experimenting with neo banking.

Venture capitalists are investing in this sector by understanding the trends in new generation neo banks. The funds in 2018 are four times higher than that of 2017.

Neo bank has been started by the author of the book named "Breaking Banks" Bright King; he started a neo bank named 'Moven'.

Major Functions of Neo Banks

A Neo-Bank is a digital bank which offers a different and, most of the time, broader user experience than traditional banks. Although the financial product offered is often similar, the interaction with it is different. It is the main value proposition for the client.

Neo-Banks are real competitors to the "traditional" banks on the market due to their reduced costs, advanced features, very user-friendly interfaces, user customization, and new technologies. Following are the innovative components of Neo-Banks.

- Fast Account Opening: - Most of the neo banks provide an account opening about 3 to 10 minutes; starting from a simple form to a video call.
- Free debit card: - Most of the neo banks offer a free debit card to the customer, and it can be managed by a mobile application fastly; blocking, changing passwords, etc.
- International Payment:- Neo banks offer to use their debit cards abroad for no fees and with a live exchange rate.
- Instant payment:- Most of the neo banks offer instant payments among their customers.
- Crypto currencies: - Some of the neo banks offer to open an account with Crypto currencies.
- Multicurrency accounts:- Some of the neo banks offer to operate an account with multiple currencies and transfer within these accounts.
- User-friendly interfaces: - Neo bank applications are user-friendly, responsive, and well designed.
- 24/7 support: - Most of the neo banks offer 24/7 international support through their app instant message system.

- Expense analytics: - Neo bank applications provide expense analytics for their customers; such as spending habits, advice on future spending, changes taken in the plans, spending meter, etc.
- Instant balance:- On the application the customer will always see an up to date balance.
- Vaults: - Neo bank helps the customer to save money for an objective. The customer can round up all the transactions and put the spare change in the vaults.

Challenges

The customer's acquisition is quite a challenge because it can be hard to convince someone to change from a regular bank to a new kind of bank. The marketing to overcome is very expensive. A lot of customers are not interested in a mobile solution and would rather have a face to face interaction or a telephone call. The major challenge for the Neo-Banks is revenue. Most if not all of the services provided by a Neo-Bank are free. Consequently, they have to find their earnings elsewhere.

Neo banks in India

1. NiYO

It offers digital banking solutions especially for salaried employees. Presently, it claims that the fin-tech start-ups cater to over five lakh customers and has partnered with 3000 corporate. Last year, the start-up launched a global card canceling the need to buy a forex card during international trips. Last month, it was collaborated with a technology-enabled financial advisory start-up, to provide investment solutions for its customers. The neo bank has also raised a little over 14 million from Prime Ventures and other investors.

2. 811 by Kotak

It is a digital bank account product by Kotak Mahindra Bank and was launched in March 2017 and is named after the day demonetization was announced in India on 8th November 2016. It is a zero maintenance bank account, along with a virtual card. The customer can earn a 6% interest on their savings. The bank has doubled its customers to 16 million with-in two years.

3. Open

Open was founded in 2017 by Mr.Anish Achuthan and Mr.Mabel Chacko with the idea of serving the underserved especially in the SME segment. The neo-bank launched its services in collaboration with ICICI bank. Now it has almost 11 banks as partners.

4. Yono by SBI

YONO (You Only Need One) is State Bank of India's digital banking platform. It was launched in November 2017. It provides not only banking services, but also lifestyle services like cab booking and online shopping. Yono launched a card less cash withdrawal facility recently. The process can be initiated using the mobile app by using a pin. Once the process is initiated from the phone, the customer can visit any of the SBI's ATM which is marked as YONO Cash and withdraw within 30 minutes of receiving the reference number on your mobile phone.

5. Instant Pay

It has started in the beginning of the Financial Year 2019-20, Instant Pay launched its neo banking solutions targeting to the SMEs sector. It will help SMEs to manage their payments, collections and financial requirements on a single interface.

Conclusion

There is a tremendous change in the banking industry in India after the entry of Neo banks. Old bankers are transferring to this type of new generation banking system by understanding the fact that there will be a changing storm in all the aspects of traditional banking. Merging and takeovers are increasing in the field of banking too, so as in the case of Whatsapp- Facebook and Flipkart-Amazon. Vadal committee appointed by Government of India recommended that the mainstream banks have to level the playing ground for the Fin- Tech Companies.

References

1. An Analytical Study on Trends and Progress of Indian banking Industry.
2. Malyadri Pand Sirisha S(2015) J Bus Fin Aff 4:136. doi:10.4172/2167-0234.1000136.
3. Implications of Fin-Tech developments for banks and bank supervisors; Basel Committee on Banking Supervision(2018) ISBN 978-92-9259-128-1\
4. Kannan R, Narain A (2001) "Determinants of net interest margin under regulatory requirements, an economic study', Economic and Political Weekly 4: 337-344.
5. Trend and Progress Report of RBI.